
Is the economic decaying leads to population decline in growth centres in the developing countries "Egypt Case?"

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ABSTRACT

The regional researches found a clear evidence that the economic decaying fellows by population decaying due to the population growth is depending mainly on the growth of the economic sector, but in developing countries the process of urbanization is different and depend on that we expected the population decaying may not fellows by population decline. In this paper, testing this relation is our goal by using some variables to measure the economic decaying/ growth besides testing other variables to measure the population decaying/ growth and find the relation between both sectors. The result is clear, there is a weak correlation between both sectors as many growth centres faced economic decaying but still have population growth and vice versa. This means the population growth is a result of the population natural increase and not a result of the economic growth.

KEY WORDS

Growth centres (GCs) – economic decaying – population decline - developing countries.

INTRODUCTION

The process of decaying is a natural process occurring in all biological and natural systems and is characteristic of any cycle, many of the researchers in different fields have tried to develop concepts and interpretation of the process of growth and decline.

The meaning of decaying

Cambridge dictionary* mentions the meaning of decay as "*to become gradually damaged, worse, or less; to cause something to do this.*" Another meaning in dictionary mentioned as "*to decrease usually gradually in size, quantity, activity, or force.*"

We can notice that decaying is mean the change in situation from strong and vigor to weak and worse it may happen gradually or suddenly depending on the atmosphere of the system or the natural of the cycle. In the literature of regions

and cities decaying, there are common three words used alternately to describe the changing process in the situation from the good to worse, as (**Decay – Decline – Shrink**).

Hoekveld, 2014 mentioned the decaying as "declining ability of a city to perform its functions and contribute to the wellbeing of the urban residents and society in general". Bradbury et al. 1982 saw the declining cities are cities in trouble, cities not economically or socially healthy as they used to be or as they should be. Schilling and Logan, 2008 define decaying cities as a "special subset of older industrial cities with significant and sustained population loss (25% or greater over the past 40 years) and increasing levels of vacant and abandoned properties, including blighted residential, commercial, and industrial buildings".

The economic decaying

The economic decaying is the drive of the other different decaying as it described by Friedrichs, 1993 as rising unemployment, rising number of persons on public assistance, and plant-closing. He also mentioned that Decline would be predicted to occur if the primary industries (companies) lose market shares. Van den Berg et al., 1982 argued about the economic decaying, is the drive of other sectors decaying. They mentioned that the common element of decaying cases is the loss of the relative economic position of the city in a wider market was the initial cause of economic decline. Consequently, the number of jobs decreased, initiating a process of selective out-migration to other areas. Hence, population decline due to migration is the consequence of economic decline. This assumption is supported by the findings of more recent case studies of urban change in European cities.

Friedrichs, 1993 confirmed the same assumption as the empirical analysis of changes in North American metropolitan areas by Rust (1975) has validated this causal effect.

Hoekveld, 2014 mentioned about the decline of the initial industry will affect all other industries related to it, resulting in an overall decline of jobs in the city. Other often-mentioned factors are socio-demographic, socio-spatial and political factors, but these are most often given a secondary role. He also mentioned the common assumption in most decaying research is the decline caused by migration is rooted in economic restructuring. The forces of globalization affect in many ways urban decline through complex socio-spatial forces. However, in most cases, the urban decay was driven by the affection of the economic decline (Pallagst et al., 2014).

The population decaying

The population decaying means the diminishing in the number of people lead to the inability of the labor structure to perform the economic functions.

This decline may happen in the developed countries due to the low of fertility and low population growth, but we correctly mean the decline, which is a result of the economic downturn and out-migration. Van den Berg et al .,1982 mentioned that people would want to live where there is employment or where employment is expected to increase in the near future; on the other hand, industries will want to establish themselves where there is an adequate supply of labor. Therefore, we can find a strong correlation between the economic and population decaying.

When there is a decline in the number of jobs the growth center lost a part of its functions, many employees migrate with their families. In the near term, the population decline noticed. However, as the economy continues to decay and labor migration continues, population decline strongly occurs.

The relation between the economic and population decline (Theoretical possibilities)

In the first possibility, it can be noticed that economic growth leads to population growth because of the movement of labor to operate the various industries. The activity of the housing market and construction sector helps to increase the demand for more employment and thus increase the migration of labor in the periphery of the growth centres to the central core. The occurrence of the regional multiplier pushing the population growth continuation and sustain economic growth.

With the passage of time and the stability of the economic structure and the market saturation shows the importance of providing economic sectors with more policies that support the technological advancement and raise the rates of competitiveness.

The second possibility occurs when population growth continues without industrial and technical development, thus losing the economic structure of competitive advantage, leading to economic decaying. Reaching this point in the growth cycle will cause successive migrations to look for other jobs in other growth centers. The closure of many factories and the contraction of employment opportunities cause the decline of population and continuation of economic decline. It is difficult to achieve economic growth unless there is interference with various policies and strategies to restore the economic structure as before and work on return the production wheel to the desired situation to ensure future for economic growth.

We note that the economic growth and decaying is followed by population growth and decline, and here lies the risk of not studying the phenomenon of decaying, which leads to many of the physical, social and economic effects that will be highlighted later.

The third possibility is the population decline may leads to economic decaying and it is challenging to create economic growth in the light of the population decline that will affect the structure of employment and the economic sector will miss for the most operational component like skilled labor.

Fig 1 The relation between the economic and population decline
 Source: performed by author based on (Hoekveld, 2014).

As in the fourth possibility, some reversal cases may happen, it is possible in the light of the economic decline, population growth will occur as a result of higher population growth rates than its economic counterpart. Most cases of this model occur in developing countries as urbanization occurs as a result of population growth and rural migration to urban areas in the light of the low rates of economic growth and decline in many cases.

In this paper will test if the case study of regional growth centers decaying in Egypt is matching the last possibility, where the economic decaying happen with population growth.

Study methodology

Study area (EGYPT)

Egypt is located in North-East of Africa with total area 1,001,450 km sq., Despite that, most of its population resides in the Nile Valley and few other locations, on only 5.7% of the total area of the country. In Africa Nigeria, Ethiopia and Egypt the most populous countries respectively, but in the Arabs world Egypt is number one in the population size. The Egyptian population witnessed a massive increase in the last century, especially when it

doubled in the previous 25 years. Being 35 million inhabitants in the 1970s, and grew to be 94,666,993 (July 2016 est.) with high population growth rate 2 % (average annual 2010-2015). Within 20 km only of the River Nile around 95% of Egyptian lives and the rest area of the country is uninhabited. Urban population is 43.1% of total population (2015), and the rate of urbanization is 1.68% annual rate of change (2010-15 est).

Egypt as a developing country faces development problems as

Population concentration

The concentration of the Egyptian population on 5.7% only of the country's area and the continuous rural migration to urban areas, led to high population densities in the urban settlements, especially within the main urban centers. This situation causes negative implications regarding the availability of sufficient housing, adequate infrastructures and the quality of services.

Regional disparities

Regarding investments for economic development, most of them go to areas of preference, with almost 40% of the development investments going to Cairo. As a result of the regional disparities especially in the investments rates

Economic pressures generated from population growth

The continuation of the current population growth rate (2.04% per annum) will lead to a population of 184 million in 2050, which require providing more than 60 million jobs. Of course, a large part of this employment is urban employment based on industrial, technological and service activities.

The imbalance in urban system

The intense concentration in the urban pattern at the national level, especially the Greater Cairo region and Alex, in addition to the imbalance in the size distribution of the urban settlements in the north and south of Egypt weaken the development capacities of the regions in both cases. The over-concentration in the urban settlements increases the pressure on resources and the difficulty of competing with the smaller settlements, which lead to urban domination. In southern Egypt, poor urban system lead to reduced opportunities for investments attraction and transfer the development to the desert periphery.

Growth centres selection

According to the latest census, the number of GCs in Egypt reached 249, It is noted in this regard that the number of GCs in Nile valley and Delta is 172 while small part in the Eastern and Western Desert. The number of GCs on which the study of indicators of growth or decaying are 60 GCs and this number covers RGCs "Governorates capitals" in addition to the growth centers that represent

economic bases at the regional level, whether industrial, agricultural or services. Besides, promising growth centers have been included, because they contain developmental capabilities, but may suffer in the current situation from developmental problems related to the investment plans.

Study spatial level "Growth Center Region or City-region"

Regional development occurs according to Friedman through the exploitation of natural resources that generate external demand and attract the investments that stimulate domestic demand and create economic savings that will lead to further expansion of productive activity and regional economic growth. Therefore, the assessment of growth center's performance should be within the region of the growth center.

Any country is considered as a unified region works as an integrated system, which in turn composite from sub-regions or sub-systems if the sub-systems developed strong inter-connectivity it will lead to the efficiency of the whole system.

Jacobs argues that city-regions are the best locations to create a new variety, due to their rich variety of economic activities: it is a cumulative process based on a growing division of labor, within the region and between regions. City-regions are more critical than nations to understand how economies evolve (Boschma & Lambooy, 1999).

Spatial analysis technique

First of all the Analyzes were performed using the software IBM SPSS Statistics 25. As a result of the nature of the study, which includes a large number of indicators were collected at different time periods ranging from 10 years started from 1976 through 1986, 1996 to 2016. This led to a number of difficulties encountered in statistical analysis as follows:

1- The difficulty to infer some indicators in a period of time without others: To find out the accuracy and correctness of the analysis, this data has been replaced by a valid statistical method through "Replace Missing Values" tool in the SPSS, which is a common method to help analyze properly and to ensure accuracy of results.

2- The existence of different values of one indicator for one GC and also the existence of many negative values: Some types of analyzes cannot deal with these negative values and do not produce correct results such as the "Trend Analysis and Time Series analysis" which aimed to use firstly. In order to deal with all these indicators and for easy comparison between them and measuring the decaying or growth of the city, "**Natural Logarithm**" was calculated for these indicators, the incident over the years, whether positive or negative for each GC. Using this type of analysis it is easy to reach a fixed value indicating the decaying or growth and understanding the nature of the change occurring for

each GC in each sector and for each indicator, which is difficult to obtain from some other analysis according to the nature of the collected data.

In order to ensure a proper measurement of the GC's growth or decay, and to arrive at accurate results aimed at reaching real conclusions, the value was reversed by multiplying it by -1 since the negative indicator indicates a decrease or decline in it and vice versa.

3- There is a difference in the reference of the values of each other: there are values that indicate the contributor to the growth and other values of the correct numbers and other ratios of other values. It affects many results and cannot be conducted on the analysis of these values and in this form, the calculation of the **"standardized scores"** for all indicators collected by the researcher and for natural logarithm resulting from the above analysis. The researcher calculates **the standard Z value**, which follows the normal distribution.

To reach a uniform number to measure the decaying or growth of the GCs, a new value based on all previous values was calculated **"Mean Value"**. Thus, each sector has one value from which the change occurring for each GC can be deduced over 50 years. Thus dividing these values into uniform statistical categories for all sectors to produce a unified index to easily compare between all sectors and more accurate final results.

Correlation analysis are used to conduct the relation between both sectors to find the strength of the this relation.

General Economic performance Growth/ Decay

The main variables used to measure Economic performance growth or decay as the following:

- Employment Growth Rate: Growth rates of economic employment 1976-1986, 1986-1996, 1996-2006 and 2006-2016 to extent growth or decline in growth rates of economic employment.
- Percentage of closed economic establishments: The percentage of closed or suspended establishments from work in all establishments as an indicator of the growth or decline of the economic performance. The indicator measured for the next periods 1986, 1996, 2006, and 2016.
- The workers in informal economic sectors: The vulnerability, fragility, and decaying of the regional economy of the growth centers is measured by the proportion of workers in informal activities. The indicator measured for the next periods 1976, 1986, 1996, 2006, and 2016.
- The attraction of investment (billion pound): The attractiveness of the business environment of the growth centre is measured by the size of the total investments directed to the economic sector.
- The number of concentrated economic functions: The number of economic functions enjoyed by the growth centre indicates the strength and the growth of the regional economy of the growth Centre.

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- Per capita GDP (pound): Measuring the per capita GDP to show the capability of the growth centres to provide an economic environment growth.
 - Financial services concentration: Index of concentration financial activities and services reflect the growth and strength of economic performance or decline at the level of growth center.

Population Growth/ decaying

The main variables used to measure the population Growth/ decaying as the following:

- Population Growth Rate: Population growth rates for the period 1976-1986, 1986-1996, 1996-2006 and finally 2006-2016 where negative growth rates reflect the decaying of economic growth centers.
- Population attraction: Population attraction is a precise indicator of the growth center's ability to attract migrants or expel others, which reflect economic growth or decline.
- Polarization of cities: It reflects the centre's ability to attract the population at the national level, which means high polarization, is a high economic weight of the growth centre at the national and regional level.
- Percentage of Arrivals of the total population: It is a reflection of the economic power of the center of growth on attraction as the first goal of migrants is to get better jobs and this indicator reflects the growth or decaying of the growth centers.

Table 1
 General Economic growth/decaying Indicators and statistical output

Markaz	economic Employment growth rate (76-86) %	economic Employment growth rate (86-96) %	economic Employment growth rate (96-06) %	Employment growth rate (00-10) %	LN economic Employment growth rate	% closed economic establishments 1986	% closed economic establishments 1996	% closed economic establishments 2006	% closed economic establishments 2016	LN % closed economic establishments %	% The workers in Informal economic sectors 1978	% The workers in Informal economic sectors 1986	% The workers in Informal economic sectors 1996	% The workers in Informal economic sectors 2006	% The workers in Informal economic sectors 2016	LN % The workers in Informal economic sectors	LN % The workers in Informal economic sectors Absolute	Financial services concentrational on 2006	The number of concentrated economic functions 2006	the attraction of investment (billion pound) 2006	Per capita GDP (pound) 2006	Zscore: LN economic Employment growth rate	Zscore: LN % closed economic establishments Absolute	Zscore: LN % The workers in Informal economic sectors	Zscore: Financial services concentrational on 2006	Zscore: the number of concentrated economic functions 2006	Zscore: the attraction of investment (billion pound) 2006	Zscore: Per capita GDP (pound) 2006	Zscores: Mean	
giza	4.38	2.40	4.47	2.01	-1.95	14.61	5.57	24.05	22.78	1.48	-1.48	3.01	4.78	1.09	2.67	0.03	-11.78	11.78	1.47	9.00	6.33	5721.84	-0.64	-0.43	-0.98	-0.11	0.17	0.16	1.03	-0.12
6 october city	3.85	35.24	15.05	14.87	3.38	0.91	2.35	17.76	14.89	9.32	-9.32	2.14	1.51	0.47	0.01	0.01	-13.34	13.34	1.21	8.00	21.10	7357.10	1.48	-2.89	-0.54	-0.26	-0.07	2.43	2.12	0.32
Bahra	3.53	3.32	1.84	1.61	-1.96	4.47	5.08	13.64	14.28	3.87	-3.87	4.18	5.29	3.92	0.01	0.01	-16.02	16.02	1.44	5.00	5.10	2657.50	-0.64	-1.18	0.21	-0.13	-0.79	-0.03	-1.03	-0.51
Qaha	3.42	3.08	3.56	3.23	-0.14	9.09	6.15	15.41	16.04	1.89	-1.89	0.39	3.11	2.07	0.00	0.00	-14.46	14.46	0.90	5.00	1.20	4861.20	0.08	-0.56	-0.23	-0.45	-0.79	-0.63	0.45	-0.30
Elobour city	3.85	4.35	48.56	14.67	3.34	0.00	6.15	1.85	2.05	0.12	-0.12	2.14	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-14.04	14.04	2.12	9.00	2.10	6673.70	1.46	0.00	-0.35	0.26	0.17	-0.49	1.66	0.39
Shobra, City	6.20	3.07	1.81	1.69	-3.25	10.75	7.31	13.10	12.80	0.58	-0.58	3.76	7.65	1.00	0.01	0.01	-13.86	13.86	1.28	11.00	11.40	4861.20	-1.15	-0.15	-0.40	-0.23	0.65	0.94	0.45	0.02
new borg elarab	3.85	6.36	18.60	6.29	1.23	9.09	8.98	36.33	29.51	3.92	-3.92	2.14	3.35	1.76	0.01	0.01	-14.74	14.74	0.46	3.00	15.30	5977.70	0.62	-1.20	-0.15	-0.71	-1.27	1.54	1.20	0.00
alex city	3.77	2.34	1.45	1.32	-2.62	12.86	14.53	23.73	24.04	2.09	-2.09	3.10	4.14	1.01	0.01	0.01	-13.93	13.93	0.99	2.00	27.40	5200.60	-0.90	-0.62	-0.38	-0.39	-1.51	3.40	0.68	0.04
Damahour	1.10	3.32	1.96	1.38	0.57	15.26	7.24	3.73	3.82	-4.62	4.62	0.26	0.43	0.33	0.00	0.00	-12.05	12.05	2.08	12.00	3.20	3455.00	0.36	1.49	-0.91	0.25	0.89	-0.32	-0.50	0.18
Kafr Eldawar	1.01	2.57	2.14	2.01	1.72	11.88	3.63	12.38	13.35	0.39	-0.39	0.74	0.41	0.47	0.00	0.01	-12.12	12.12	0.60	8.00	12.00	4474.40	0.82	-0.09	-0.89	-0.63	-0.07	1.03	0.19	0.05
Gharb Nobareya	3.85	6.36	9.81	4.20	0.22	9.09	52.35	36.55	10.14	0.36	-0.36	2.14	3.35	0.00	0.00	0.00	-21.47	21.47	0.20	3.00	3.40	4704.40	0.22	-0.08	1.74	-0.86	-1.27	-0.29	0.34	-0.03
Badr	4.25	3.22	2.47	2.01	-1.87	9.09	6.15	0.12	0.82	-8.02	8.02	1.14	2.57	5.46	0.00	0.00	-14.94	14.94	0.48	3.00	4.10	3031.70	-0.61	2.56	-0.09	-0.70	-1.27	-0.18	-0.78	-0.15
Marsa Matrouh	3.85	3.13	8.64	3.42	-0.30	22.27	2.38	23.76	20.76	-0.23	0.23	2.14	4.81	0.80	0.01	0.01	-13.32	13.32	1.58	13.00	24.00	3841.00	0.02	0.11	-0.55	-0.05	1.12	-0.45	-0.24	0.00
Eldaba	3.85	15.99	-4.95	1.05	-3.25	4.37	0.13	18.99	19.26	4.94	-4.94	2.14	5.71	0.08	0.00	0.00	-19.44	19.44	0.25	3.00	0.98	4649.10	-1.15	-1.52	1.17	-0.83	-1.27	-0.66	0.31	-0.57
Elaimein	3.85	6.51	-10.65	8.94	2.11	9.09	7.97	77.23	24.58	3.31	-3.31	2.14	5.78	0.26	0.00	0.00	-19.73	19.73	0.00	2.00	1.10	4464.50	0.97	-1.01	1.26	-0.98	-1.51	-0.65	0.18	-0.25
Kafr elshekh	2.31	1.87	0.95	0.87	-2.44	17.66	0.69	7.25	6.89	-3.14	3.14	1.46	3.49	0.60	0.00	0.00	-14.40	14.40	1.68	12.00	2.10	4622.10	-0.83	1.02	-0.25	0.01	0.89	-0.49	0.29	0.09
Dosouk	1.67	2.52	1.82	1.74	0.10	7.99	1.61	1.47	1.63	-5.30	5.30	3.62	1.92	0.45	0.00	0.00	-20.03	20.03	1.97	13.00	1.90	4729.50	0.18	1.70	1.34	0.19	1.12	-0.52	0.36	0.62
Elmansoura	3.15	3.04	0.53	0.49	-4.65	8.20	2.36	7.21	8.98	0.30	-0.30	1.52	5.08	2.44	0.00	0.01	-12.88	12.88	1.99	10.00	6.10	3372.30	-1.71	-0.06	-0.67	0.20	0.41	0.12	-0.55	-0.32
Aga	2.99	2.88	1.25	1.14	-2.41	2.91	2.79	1.88	1.65	-1.89	1.89	1.12	2.53	1.88	0.00	0.00	-15.36	15.36	0.91	8.00	1.10	2425.60	-0.82	0.63	0.03	-0.44	-0.07	-0.65	-1.17	-0.36
Damietta	1.58	2.18	1.58	1.21	-0.67	8.05	5.57	3.76	4.94	-1.63	1.63	1.77	2.64	0.42	0.00	0.00	-18.96	18.96	0.87	4.00	1.20	4087.90	-0.13	0.55	1.04	-0.46	-1.03	-0.63	-0.09	-0.10
New demieta	3.85	42.69	17.71	12.54	2.95	0.00	1.30	8.82	6.49	0.12	-0.12	2.14	5.88	0.68	0.00	0.00	-17.32	17.32	3.28	11.00	0.87	3819.30	1.31	0.00	0.58	0.96	0.65	-0.68	-0.25	0.37
Tanta	3.46	2.21	1.61	1.54	-2.02	9.37	5.69	6.57	6.78	-1.08	1.08	2.02	3.13	0.56	0.00	0.00	-15.05	15.05	0.42	1.00	4.30	4267.80	-0.67	0.38	-0.06	-0.73	-1.75	-0.15	0.05	-0.42
Elmahala_Elkob	2.78	2.86	1.19	1.24	-2.02	11.34	5.26	4.47	5.03	-2.71	2.71	1.84	2.84	0.62	0.00	0.00	-18.56	18.56	6.72	14.00	4.10	4137.80	-0.66	0.89	0.92	3.00	1.36	-0.18	-0.04	0.76
Kafr Elzayat	4.17	0.49	1.38	1.31	-2.89	5.66	3.30	8.90	8.81	1.47	-1.47	0.86	1.99	0.69	0.00	0.00	-14.92	14.92	9.75	12.00	3.50	3308.70	-1.01	-0.43	-0.10	4.79	0.89	-0.28	-0.59	0.47
Zefta	5.42	0.11	1.92	1.77	-2.80	12.15	1.49	0.68	1.49	-7.00	7.00	0.81	2.84	0.70	0.00	0.00	-11.01	11.01	7.02	14.00	2.10	3294.60	-0.97	2.24	0.49	3.17	1.36	-0.49	-0.60	0.74
Shibin elkom	2.65	3.86	1.39	1.31	-1.76	8.04	2.84	1.98	1.79	-5.01	5.01	0.86	3.18	0.71	0.00	0.01	-17.66	17.66	1.30	9.00	2.90	4170.10	-0.56	1.61	-1.02	-0.21	0.17	-0.37	-0.02	-0.06
Elzagazig	3.85	32.14	8.31	4.98	0.84	9.54	10.47	8.35	7.77	-0.68	0.68	2.14	0.00	0.35	0.00	0.00	-15.20	15.20	0.79	4.00	8.90	3637.50	0.39	0.25	-0.02	-0.51	-1.03	0.55	-0.37	-1.11
Elshayeb	1.66	2.61	4.45	3.78	2.06	9.34	5.17	6.93	7.14	-0.90	0.90	1.47	3.35	0.87	0.00	0.00	-16.63	16.63	1.68	13.00	4.80	4098.60	0.95	0.32	0.38	0.01	1.12	-0.08	-0.06	0.38
Elasher_Men_Ra	3.85	18.46	9.91	6.53	1.32	2.54	4.13	17.61	15.23	5.97	-5.97	2.14	5.47	0.55	0.00	0.01	-13.77	13.77	1.52	8.00	17.50	5441.70	0.66	-1.84	-0.42	-0.08	-0.07	1.88	0.84	0.14
Madeinet_Elsah	3.85	29.12	7.90	5.24	0.77	3.70	3.80	5.88	5.51	1.39	-1.39	2.14	1.54	0.49	0.00	0.01	-13.20	13.20	0.51	3.00	3.80	4403.40	0.44	-0.40	-0.58	-0.68	-1.27	-0.26	0.14	-0.37
Esmailya	4.99	3.18	2.88	3.97	-0.57	6.69	6.41	11.46	12.08	1.97	-1.97	3.59	1.99	1.27	0.00	0.01	-15.86	15.86	1.33	13.00	0.70	4627.30	-0.09	-0.58	0.17	-0.19	1.12	-0.71	0.29	0.00
Aereeh	3.85	6.48	2.76	2.15	-1.46	9.09	4.19	3.04	9.75	0.23	-0.23	2.14	3.77	0.40	0.00	0.01	-12.78	12.78	1.65	12.00	0.20	4764.10	-0.44	-0.04	-0.70	-0.01	0.89	-0.78	0.38	-0.10
Kafr Elabd	13.66	8.62	6.43	4.56	-2.74	9.09	1.33	5.26	7.14	-0.81	0.81	13.13	4.57	0.13	0.00	0.00	-26.00	26.00	0.75	4.00	0.34	3727.60	-0.95	0.29	3.02	-0.54	-1.03	-0.76	-0.31	-0.04
Eltoor	3.85	7.04	8.06	5.02	0.66	9.09	6.59	8.99	9.13	0.01	-0.01	2.14	2.20	0.19	0.00	0.00	-19.44	19.44	2.75	8.00	1.80	4648.86	0.40	0.03	1.17	0.65	-0.07	-0.54	0.30	0.28
Sharm_elSheikh	3.85	14.64	30.37	12.79	3.00	9.09	1.85	5.01	7.42	-0.68	0.68	2.14	2.85	42.94	0.00	0.02	-11.62	11.62	0.54	3.00	5.20	9143.16	1.33	0.25	-1.03	-0.66	-1.27	-0.01	3.32	0.28
Elfayoum	2.70	2.70	2.84	2.72	0.02	11.42	5.61	14.77	15.15	0.94	-0.94	0.75	2.13	0.41	0.00	0.00	-15.22	15.22	2.13	13.00	2.10	2316.20	0.14	-0.26	-0.01	0.28	1.12	-0.49	-1.26	-0.07
Bany_Soweif	3.32	3.52	3.54	3.42	0.07	6.98	10.15	14.20	14.78	2.50	-2.50	1.49	2.36	0.89	0.00	0.00	-19.16	19.16	2.05	13.00	1.90	2859.90	0.17	-0.75	1.09	0.24	1.12	-0.52	-0.89	0.06
New_bany_soweif	3.85	6.36	57.33	21.49	4.30	9.09	0.00	1.60	1.74	-5.51	5.51	2.14	3.35	0.00	0.00	0.00	-19.44	19.44	3.09	11.00	3.20	3897.20	1.84	1.77	1.17	0.85	0.65	-0.32	-0.20	0.82
Elmenya	2.66	2.49	2.44	2.38	-0.28	10.34	7.23	17.04	18.12	1.87	-1.87	3.03	3.19	0.60	0.00	0.00	-20.30	20.30	1.47	13.00	4.10	3079.20	0.03	-0.55	1.42	-0.11	1.12	-0.18	-0.75	0.14
New_menya	3.85	6.36	52.30	27.85	4.95	9.09	0.00	7.60	5.67	-1.57	1.57	2.14	3.35	0.00	0.01	0.01	-13.34	13.34	4.33	9.00	4.40	2451.30	2.10	0.53	-0.54	1.58	0.1			

Table 2
 Population growth/decaying indicators and statistical output

Markaz	Population growth rate				P.GR.LN	P.A_1	A.P_1	P.P.C_1	Z.P.A_1	Z.A.P_1	Z.P.P.C_1	Z.P.GR.LN	Mean. Zscores
	76-86 P.G1	86-96 P.G1	96-05 P.G1	06-16 P.G1									
giza	4.25	2.46	1.32	1.89	-2.70114	-0.57678	23.37819	0.24599	-0.41696	0.07501	-0.74322	-0.15576	-0.31
6 october city	N.E	32.36	15.86	13.78	-4.26852	14.05024	67.53389	3.97289	0.77089	1.82123	1.01704	-0.31003	0.82
Banha	2.66	1.64042	1.4921	1.42	-2.09223	-0.76793	0.66382	0.70974	-0.43249	-0.82328	-0.52418	-0.09583	-0.47
Qaha	2.68	2.06	1.5466	1.49	-1.9568	-0.71340	3.17487	0.73356	-0.42806	-0.72397	-0.51293	-0.08250	-0.44
Elobour city	N.E	-0.3	45.908	14.87	-11.2729	43.64801	86.52064	5.03790	3.17450	2.57209	1.52005	-0.99943	1.57
Shobra_City	6.52	1.62	1.65	1.58	-4.72483	-0.41385	24.36176	0.86192	-0.40373	0.11390	-0.45231	-0.35494	-0.27
new borg elarab	N.E	N.E	19.439	6.21	-11.4115	17.69948	46.31190	4.28320	1.06724	0.98196	1.16360	-1.01307	0.55
alex city	2.32	1.23391	2.0263	2.1	-0.3321	0.28633	6.26488	0.93715	-0.34687	-0.60177	-0.41678	0.07741	-0.32
Damahour	1.0243	1.03463	1.5416	1.43	1.11221	-0.62835	1.13602	0.73140	-0.42115	-0.80460	-0.51395	0.21957	-0.38
Kafr Eldawar	2.9241	1.7642	1.2452	1.21	-2.94125	-0.92481	1.35988	0.60010	-0.44523	-0.79575	-0.57597	-0.17939	-0.50
Gharb Nobareya	N.E	N.E	19.648	4.73	-14.2404	17.47788	57.21967	4.29828	1.04924	1.41333	1.17072	-1.29151	0.59
Badr	3.28	3.2	3.83	3.73	0.428549	1.69000	30.07287	5.15580	-0.23288	0.33976	1.57574	0.15228	0.46
Marsa Matrouh	2.14	2.18	11.78	3.45	1.591895	4.75274	15.64762	2.91805	0.01584	-0.23071	0.51882	0.26678	0.14
Eldabaa	2.12	13.22	-4.5	1.74	-0.65844	-6.42000	1.59018	-1.46000	-0.89149	-0.78664	-1.54898	0.04529	-0.80
Elalamein	5.6066	20.8344	-24.11	10.34	2.040224	-28.06000	6.97279	-7.60000	-2.64886	-0.57378	-4.44896	0.31090	-1.84
Kafr elshekh	2.92	1.91	1.6721	1.68	-1.84263	-0.76788	0.33262	0.78785	-0.43248	-0.83637	-0.48729	-0.07126	-0.46
Dosouk	2.9312	1.54782	1.581	1.62	-1.97665	-0.85900	0.63987	0.74851	-0.43988	-0.82422	-0.50587	-0.08445	-0.46
Elmansoura	2.0424	1.52553	1.749	1.59	-0.83463	1.28899	4.48931	0.82074	-0.26545	-0.67199	-0.47176	0.02795	-0.35
Aga	0.37	1.13	1.2294	1.17	3.83752	0.76936	1.45596	0.59300	-0.30765	-0.79195	-0.57932	0.48780	-0.30
Damietta	2.0044	2.13148	8.0729	2.47	0.696275	4.43288	2.23067	2.78372	-0.01013	-0.76131	0.45538	0.17863	-0.03
New demieta	N.E	45.44	15.281	13.71	-5.99134	-11.64071	78.34098	3.91206	0.57521	2.24861	0.98831	-0.47960	0.83
Tanta	1.7349	1.03171	1.2653	1.29	-0.98767	-0.51471	2.70670	0.60917	-0.41192	-0.74249	-0.57169	0.01289	-0.43
Elmahala	2.13	0.92	1.1544	1.21	-1.88501	-0.62557	1.91051	0.55909	-0.42093	-0.77397	-0.59534	-0.07543	-0.47
Kafr Elzayat	2.6055	1.25135	0.7725	0.82	-3.85364	-1.00748	1.69506	0.38188	-0.45194	-0.78249	-0.67904	-0.26919	-0.55
Zefta	3.1963	1.56222	1.4884	1.41	-2.72799	-0.29159	1.13691	0.70814	-0.39381	-0.80457	-0.52494	-0.15840	-0.47
Shebin elkom	2.5513	1.71627	1.2259	1.2	-2.51425	-0.70405	2.10327	0.59146	-0.42730	-0.76635	-0.58005	-0.13737	-0.48
Elsadat	N.E	25.4606	10.085	5.89	-7.31939	8.15469	23.60231	3.18326	0.29211	0.08387	0.64408	-0.61031	0.10
Elzaqazeeg	1.89	0.91	1.2498	1.31	-1.22183	-1.24725	3.36240	0.60219	-0.47141	-0.71655	-0.57498	-0.01016	-0.44
Elasher Ramada	N.E	18.85	10.163	7.43	-4.65494	7.66624	74.24555	3.19728	0.25245	2.08665	0.65071	-0.34806	0.66
Elsalheya	N.E	33.17	8.8215	4.64	-9.83466	6.32445	55.17223	2.94194	0.14348	1.33236	0.53011	-0.85787	0.29
Esmailiya	3.83	1.83	1.4	1.51	-3.10252	3.79976	60.89955	2.33849	-0.06155	1.55886	0.24509	-0.19527	0.39
Areesh	UN.AV	4.1	3.48	2.98	-1.59532	3.03193	18.53454	1.41887	-0.12390	-0.11654	-0.18926	-0.04692	-0.12
Beer Elabd	11.55	5.44	5.8721	4.72	-2.98292	5.63308	18.65751	2.24185	0.08733	-0.11168	0.19945	-0.18349	0.00
Eltoor	UN.AV	9.59	6.4988	5.44	-2.83471	6.36882	50.06769	2.40887	0.14708	1.13049	0.27833	-0.16891	0.35
Sharm elSheikh	UN.AV	17.36	24.484	15.33	-0.62179	24.35409	16.89682	4.57882	1.60765	-0.18131	1.30323	0.04890	0.69
Elfayoom	2.47	2.04	1.9353	1.87	-0.9276	-0.46268	0.79139	0.89934	-0.40770	-0.81823	-0.43464	0.01880	-0.41
Bany Soweif	2.6	1.2	1.18	1.15	-2.71917	-1.07671	3.24501	0.58078	-0.45756	-0.72120	-0.58509	-0.15753	-0.48
New bany sowe	N.E	UN.AV	56.15	6.78	-21.1405	53.61830	76.51094	5.09500	3.98418	2.17624	1.54702	-1.97064	1.43
Elmenya	2.04	1.18037	1.5979	1.54	-0.93722	-0.32214	1.39581	0.75582	-0.39629	-0.79433	-0.50242	0.01785	-0.42
New menya	N.E	UN.AV	52.304	12.25	-14.5155	50.38432	9.87519	5.07903	3.72155	-0.45899	1.53948	-1.31858	0.87
Assiut	2.48	2.35894	1.2549	1.38	-1.95392	-1.33510	3.03908	0.60450	-0.47855	-0.72934	-0.57389	-0.08222	-0.47
New Asyout	N.E	N.E	N.E	54.34	4.55767	64.33844	5.15580	0.00000	1.69486	1.57574	5.45848	2.18	
Elkharga	3.76	2.53	2.0523	1.91	-2.25772	-0.07773	16.12319	0.94786	-0.37644	-0.21191	-0.41172	-0.11212	-0.28
Eldakhla	3.88	3.17	2.3188	2.27	-1.78685	0.19000	5.22262	1.05618	-0.35470	-0.64299	-0.36056	-0.06577	-0.36
Elfarafra	4.86	1.26	5.42	2.99	-1.61922	3.39000	60.62472	2.17028	-0.09483	1.54799	0.16565	-0.04927	0.39
Sohag	2.6	2.54	1.26	1.31	-2.28495	-1.21923	1.57288	0.53461	-0.46914	-0.78733	-0.60690	-0.11480	-0.49
New Souhag	N.E	N.E	N.E	40.38	40.38	4.55767	61.28000	5.15580	0.00000	1.57390	1.57574	4.08447	1.81
Qena	2.5	2.62	2.6173	2.49	-0.01336	0.58735	3.54898	1.17392	-0.32243	-0.70918	-0.30495	0.10878	-0.31
Nagea Hamady	3.91	1.57	3.0804	2.91	-0.98461	1.05041	1.67585	1.34922	-0.28482	-0.78325	-0.22215	0.01319	-0.32
Ddeshna	2.65	1.5	1.7596	2.08	-0.80731	-0.27036	0.53590	0.82528	-0.39208	-0.82833	-0.46961	0.03064	-0.41
Luxor	3.01	2	2.7782	2.54	-0.56592	0.75825	1.29647	1.23582	-0.30855	-0.79826	-0.27571	0.05440	-0.33
Teiba	N.E	N.E	N.E	2.79	2.79	4.55767	1.39690	5.15580	0.00000	-0.79428	1.57574	0.38470	0.29
Aswan	2.84	1.47575	1.8404	1.78	-1.5573	0.14037	7.22113	0.85948	-0.35873	-0.56395	-0.45346	-0.04318	-0.35
Toshka	N.E	N.E	N.E	4.89	4.89	4.55767	21.48153	5.15580	0.00000	0.00000	1.57574	0.59139	0.54
Hurgada	7.29	5.33	10.352	2.64	-3.38575	8.33676	34.14584	3.23048	-0.30690	0.50083	0.66639	-0.22314	0.31
Ras Ghareb	3.92	2.81	1.67	1.59	-3.00786	-0.51000	20.37443	0.71641	-0.41154	-0.04378	-0.52104	-0.18595	-0.29
Elqosier	4.52	0.47	5.7	2.31	-2.23755	3.51000	20.17817	2.14397	-0.08508	-0.05154	0.15322	-0.11013	-0.02
portsaid city	4.28	1.67317	1.9163	2.5	-1.79221	0.36627	33.95390	0.89137	-0.34038	0.49324	-0.43840	-0.06630	-0.09
elsuey city	5.36	2.47964	2.0634	3.52	-1.40168	0.10339	37.85818	0.95244	-0.36173	0.64765	-0.40955	-0.02786	-0.04
cairo city	1.78	1.07391	1.2808	1.81	0.055712	-0.47921	10.51606	0.61600	-0.40904	-0.43365	-0.56846	0.11558	-0.32

Results and discussion

The economic decaying

1- The number of economic growth centers from the perspective of the performance of the economy is (14 centers), including centers with strong and weak growth represented 23.3% of the total centres.

2- The number of decaying centres is equal to the growth centres 14 centre

represented 23.3% of the total including the decaying and sever decaying centres.

Fig 2 the analysis of the values of the index of economic sector growth or decay

Source: Author

3- A large number of centers classified as economic stagnation from the point of view of economic performance, which reached 32 centers represented 53.3 %.

4- The large number of the growth centres classified as economic stagnation centers, and it covers the most parts in the country in Nile valley as well as in Nile Delta.

5- The mega million cities such as Giza, Alexandria, Shobra and Suez suffering from economic stagnation, this mean the big economic base under the risk of decaying and the opportunities of growth are few.

6- Few growth centres present good chance of economic growth and Cairo still playing a significant role to push the regional and national economy.

7- The new cities represented their success as economic growth centers despite their modernity as one of the most important centers of industrial and service leadership. This allows a strong investment environment to maintain their workers, growth rates and economic facilities such as New Demmitta, October, Al Oobor, and others.

8- It is clear that most of the growth and economic leadership centers from the perspective of economic performance are concentrated in the north of Egypt while there are no growth centers or economic leadership in southern Egypt only some of the new cities. This indicates the need for completion of urban renewal and the creation of a number of medium cities In the Suez Canal region and the northern Delta region.

9- Most of the growth centres in the border and desert governorates suffer from stagnation and economic decaying, including Red Sea's cities, except the growth centres of South Sinai like Sharm and Al Tur.

Fig 3 the spatial diffusion of the economic growth/ decaying in the growth centres, Source: Author

The population decaying

1- The number of GCS of very high and high socio-economic characteristics that reflect the real standards of living at the national level is (15 centers) represent 25% of the total

2- A large number of centers with medium, decaying and sever decaying socio-economic characteristics is (45 centres) represent 75%.

3- Most centers with higher socio-economic characteristics are in the periphery and border areas as in the Red Sea and Sinai region such as Sharm El Shaykh and Al Tur and North Sinai such as Arish and Bair al Abd as well as GCs of the northern coast.

4- It is worth mentioning that most of the major cities in size have decreased their living standards and have a low and very low standard of living. Most of the major cities include governorates capitals such as Alexandria / Al Mansourah / Al Zaqaq / Suez / Asyut / Shbain El Kuwm / Sawhaj and Qinah. In contrast, most of the emerging tourism centers have increased their living standards despite the industrial / tourist / agricultural decline / low levels of economic performance - but they are all among the best centers of living standards such as A Arish / Sharm El Shaykh / Ghardaqa / Tur / Al Dakhla.

Fig 4 the analysis of the values of the index of population growth or decay
Source: Author

5- The socio-economic characteristics have been decayed in large areas of the Egyptian context. This has been formed a range of areas of decaying living standards including East Delta regions such as (Al Mansouras and Zaqaq), the full West Delta region and the North of Delta except for the city of New Demietta, in addition to the surrounding areas of Greater Cairo, except October.

6- Despite, the new growth centers have their distinct social dimensions and growth opportunities, but most of them classified as medium socio-economic characteristics centers, especially in the Nile valley like new Minya, new Sawhaj.

Fig 5 the spatial diffusion of the population growth/ decaying in the growth centres

Source: Author

The correlation between the economic and the population decaying

There is weak a correlation "0.053" between the economic and population decaying as many of the economically decaying centers have achieved high population growth such as the Mahalla, Shebin and Zefta and vice versa. Here, we note that most of the studies that have taken place on the cities decaying are due primarily to the migration that occurred as a result of the economic decline. However, we find that the economic decaying in Egypt occurs in the light of population growth or in the light of housing stability and not due to economic growth. Population growth is caused by the existence of demographic and demographic pressures that lead to continued population growth.

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